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Performance of commercial rice varieties in lowlands of western Venezuela

L. E. Alvarez Larrauri, Universidad Ezequiel Zamora, UNELLEZ, Guanare, Estado Portuguesa, Venezuela

We evaluated the response of rice varieties Cimarron, Araure 4, Oryzica 3, Oryzica 1, Oryzica Llanos 5, and La Toma to increasing N levels. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with varieties in the main plots and N levels in subplots during the 1993 wet season.

Soil was an Inceptisol with 4.7% organic matter, pH 5.8, 10 ppm P, 147 ppm K, and 53.4% clay content in the upper 17 cm. Rice was dry seeded at 160 kg/ha in a farmer's field. Half of the N dose, 20.2 kg P/ha as P₂O₅, and 49.8 kg K/ha as K₂O were broadcast and incorporated into the soil at sowing. The other half of the N dose was applied at panicle

Grain and milling yield and yield components of 6 commercial rice varieties.^a Guanare, Venezuela. 1993 wet season.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Head rice (%)	Broken grain (%)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	1,000-grain weight (g)
Oryzica 3	5.3 a	57.5 ab	6.7 cd	224.2 bc	126.0 a	19.8 c
Oryzica Llanos 5	5.2 ab	59.7 a	4.5 e	233.6 bc	80.4 c	28.2 a
Araure 4	4.8 bc	58.8 ab	5.2 de	240.0 abc	80.0 c	25.4 b
La Toma	4.6 cd	56.8 b	7.6 c	245.3 ab	105.0 b	18.1 c
Cimarron	3.9 e	51.1 c	16.1 a	263.6 a	62.0 cd	24.5 b
Oryzica 1	3.6 e	56.9 ab	9.9 b	215.6 c	70.0 cd	23.7 b
CV (%)	14.1	5.6	7.9	12.3	16.0	9.7

^aNumbers in a column followed by the same letter are not different according to LSD test at P = 0.05.

initiation. Rice was sown on 31 Mar and the first irrigation was on 1 Apr. The field was flooded on 8 May and the water level was kept at 20 cm until harvest. Cimarron and Oryzica 1 were harvested on 6 Aug, Oryzica 3 and La Toma on 16 Aug, and Araure 4 and Oryzica Llanos 5 on 20 Aug.

Oryzica 3 and Oryzica Llanos 5 produced the highest grain yields (see

table), rice grain yield response increased up to 120 kg N/ha. Oryzica Llanos 5 produced the highest head rice yield, lowest % broken grains, and highest grain weight. Oryzica 3 produced the most grains/panicle. Araure 4 lodged severely.

Pyricularia grisea, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Cercospora oryzae*, and *Ustilago indica* affected Cimarron and Oryzica 1. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Three rice varieties of medium duration released for rainfed lowland areas in Cambodia

R. C. Chaudhary, Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Rice Project, P. O. Box 1, Phnom Penh, Cambodia; M. Sarom, O. Makara, S. Sovith, and P. K. Hel, Ministry of Agriculture, Phnom Penh, Cambodia

Cambodia grows rainfed lowland rice of medium duration on about 30% of its area. Popular varieties of medium duration are usually weakly photoperiod sensitive with less than 150 d duration. No recommended modern varieties of medium duration were previously available in the country, so a massive varietal introduction and testing program was initiated in 1989. More than 11,000 introduced and indigenous varieties were tested during 1989-92 using a multi-locational approach and a four-tier testing system: observational yield trials, preliminary yield trials, advanced yield trials, and on-farm adaptive trials (OFAT).

Three varieties performed very well and were released in 1992 as Santepheap

Table 1. Yield (t/ha) of Santepheap 1, Santepheap 2, and Santepheap 3 compared with that of checks in varietal trials in Cambodia. 1989-92.

Variety	Year (no. of locations)			
	1989 (3)	1990 (15)	1991 (17)	1992 (87)
Santepheap 1	5.0 a ^a	3.5 b	4.0 b	2.7 ± 0.22
Santepheap 2	4.0 c	4.1 a	3.9 b	3.1 ± 0.27
Santepheap 3	4.8 b	3.5 b	4.2 a	3.2 ± 0.21
Check (IR42, locals)	3.1 d	3.1 c	3.5 c	2.6 ± 0.22
CV (%)	9.0	12.0	11.3	-

^aValues with a common letter in the same column are not significantly different by DMRT.

Table 2. Main characteristics of the recommended rice varieties.

Characteristic	Santepheap 1	Santepheap 2	Santepheap 3
Duration (d)	131 WS ^a	135 WS	137 WS
Height (cm)	108	108	106
Vegetative vigor score	4	3	4
Panicle length (cm)	24	24	24
Grains per panicle (no.)	110	102	105
100-grain weight (g)	2.7	2.7	2.5
Grain size (L×B in mm)	6.8 × 2.2	6.8 × 2.2	6.1 × 2.6
Grain type ^b	LS	LS	LB
Leafhopper damage score	4	2	3
Gall midge damage score	6	6	5
BPH reaction ^c	R	R	R
GLH reaction ^c	R	R	R
Tungro reaction ^c	MR	MR	R
Blast reaction ^c	MR	MR	MR
Phenotypic acceptability	4	4	3

^aWS = weakly photoperiod sensitive. ^bLS = long slender, LB = long bold. ^cR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

(Khmer word for peace) 1, Santepheap 2, and Santepheap 3. Santepheap 1 (IR43342-10-1-1-3-3) is a cross of Meedom Hmwe/IR21313-39-3-2; Santepheap 2 (IR45411-40-2-1), a cross of SPR7215-1-25-1-5/IR20925-238-2; and Santepheap 3 (OR142-99), a cross of Pankaj/Sigadis. All three entries were introduced through International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice nurseries in Cambodia.

During 1989 tests at three locations and 1990 tests at 15 locations, the varieties outyielded the checks (Table 1).

More than 100 farmers tested the varieties in OFAT during 1992 using their best medium varieties as checks. Eighty-seven farmers gave their yields and reactions; 54 of them grew the trial with no fertilizer application. Average yield of Santepheap 1 was 2.7 t/ha; Santepheap 2, 3.1 t/ha; and Santepheap 3, 3.2 t/ha compared with 2.6 t/ha for the best check. The yield advantage was much higher for the 33 farmers who grew the varieties using fertilizer.

When asked to choose the best variety, 57 farmers picked Santepheap 1, 62

farmers picked Santepheap 2, and 69 farmers picked Santepheap 3 over their best medium variety.

Morphoagronomic and resistance characteristics of these varieties, scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, are in Table 2. The varieties have reasonable levels of resistance to brown planthopper, green leafhopper, leafhopper, gall midge, blast, and tungro. Farmers are rapidly adapting these varieties on large areas in Cambodia. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Jaldi Dhan: an extra early rice suitable for upland production

S. N. Chakrabarti, Genetics Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi 110012, India

A series of Jaldi Dhan (JD) varieties has been developed through radiation-induced mutant genes, mostly derived from traditional cultivars (Table 1). These types showed superior harvest index and productivity efficiency over tall traditional varieties (Table 2). They have appreciable tolerance for moisture stress, are very early (60-80 d to maturity), have aggressive early vigor to suppress weed growth, and possess

adaptability to low fertilizer and water inputs. Their capacity to produce biomass under adverse conditions is considerably higher than that of modern varieties.

Based on their desirable performance in the national coordinated program during 1988-92, JD3 and JD8 were recommended for on-farm programs in various upland areas.

Jaldi Dhan varieties have changed rice production scenarios in drought-prone uplands, flood-prone areas, high altitude areas, coastal lands, and tracts with problem soils. These varieties are useful for increasing upland productivity, as a short-duration dry season (DS) or wet season (WS) crop, and in postjute and postpotato rotations. They may also be

used as a contingency crop in areas affected by natural calamities, as a quick crop between two major crops to increase per unit production, and as a component crop in two successive rice crops in the same WS, particularly in areas where only single rice crops are usually grown.

In the famine-prone Kalahandi District of Orissa, farmers could harvest yields of 3.5 t/ha with JD5 and JD6, which is double the yield of the traditional local variety, Satika. In Manipur, JD1 produced stable yields of about 4 t/ha. JD3 has become popular in coastal areas of Parganas District in West Bengal as an early DS crop because it can be harvested before salinity becomes a problem.

At Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, JD3 was the highest yielding extra early type, producing up to 4.6 t/ha under direct seeded, puddled conditions in DS. With its tolerance for moisture-stress conditions, JD3 is capable of producing 2 t/ha with less than 500 mm of rain. JD8 had a yield potential of more than 3 t/ha in rainfed uplands in Bihar.

An important feature of the Jaldi Dhan plant type is its superior response at low input applications. The response of JD3 was 48% in WS and 91.6% in DS more than that of semidwarf Ratna when 30 kg N/ha was applied. ■

Table 1. Features of Jaldi Dhan (JD) varieties.

Variety	Cross	Days to maturity	Height group ^a	Potential yield (t/ha) ^b
JD1 (PNR570-17)	Gora M ^c / MW-10M//N-22M	60-75	MT	4.5
JD3 (PNR555-5)	Dular M/N-22// PNR351/Mtu-17 M	65-75	MT	5.3
JD4 (PNR580-6)	Kalinga III// PNR-351/MW-10M	65-75	MT	3.9
JD5 (PNR556-26)	Dular M/N-22MM// MW-10 M	70-75	SD	2.7
JD6 (PNR551-4)	Dular M/N-22 M	65-70	SD	3.5
JD8 (PNR550-1-2)	Dular M/N-22 M	70-75	MT	4.2
JD10 (PNR555-28)	Dular M/N-22// PNR351/Mtu-17 M	75-80	SD	5.8

^aMT = medium tall (≥ 110 cm), SD = semidwarf (< 110 cm). ^bPotential yield represents the maximum grain yield obtained in coordinated trials or in on-farm trials. ^cM = mutant induced by gamma radiation.